

Semiotics of Sasak Puppets (Study of Sasak Puppets Kembang Kuning East Lombok)

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to investigate the meaning and symbolic values of Jayengrana actor in Wong Menak Wayang Sasak story. This study is descriptive qualitative using observation, interview, and documentation as data collection techniques. To obtain the meaning, the researcher use semiotic perspective method analysis from Roland Barthes' theory. After significance analysis is done, a conclusion can be drawn that the symbolic values of the Jayengrana character are interpreted through naming and characterization in playing his main actor role. Each name of the actor reflects his identity or personality which is reflected from character shows on their performance.

KEYWORDS: Semiotics, Jayengrana, Sasak Puppets

INTRODUCTION

Wayang/ puppets is a kinds of art show that full of aesthetic values offers two aspects, those are audio and visual aspect. Many radio program broadcast wayang stories by hearing the wayang conversations actor in which accompanied by special music and songs to enhance the atmosphere that the puppeteer wants to create many times. By listening only, sometimes the listeners are satisfied and able to capture the storyline and atmosphere is created by the puppeteer's performance.

From visuals aspect, this performance offers more beauty that can be enjoyed by the audiens, this makes wayang performances more interesting. But still going on. The art of wayang performance also containing a full of moral lessons/messages indirectly. These moral values are implied through the actor, characters, dialogue, and even the use of music to accompany the performance. In fact, wayang is a highly symbolic performance can lead big problems if any misunderstanding of the symbols interpretation displayed on the performance. Besides presenting various kinds of art, Puppets also a tools of communication as way to express soul feeling or moral values that the puppeteer wants to convey. These moral values are conveyed implicitly through the story they presents, so the fans or audiens will be able to get enlightened about many things to lead them to the perfection life through the teachings of wisdom contained in it.

There are many stories presents in the shows, one of them is Wong Menak story. For Sasak people, they believe Wong Menak story and jayengrane are same, but in fact both are quietly different. Wong Menak story is story tells about the noblemen life in which Jayengrane actor is become symbol of their nobility. Wong Menak story is a story that tells the Amir Ambyah saga. Jayengrane become the actor ofthe story. The story of Amir Ambyah or commonly known as Amir Hamzah is taken from the book of Qissai Emr Hamza which is the result of Malay literature originating from Persia and written in Kawi language.

As explained above, Wong Menak story in this wayang sasak show contains of many messages or lessons, therefor to explore the meaning and purposing conveyed in the show, it needs a tool. One of the tools commonly used in this case is semiotics.

In linguistics, we find out term semiotics. Semiotics is the study of signs. It studies of systems, rules and conventions that allow signs to have meaning. It means, every movement, action, sound, symbol or anything displayed in show has a sign, signifier and the signifie transfers meaning to all fans. Saussure focused his thoughts on language and its implementation in human life. In this case, wayang is a form of language implementation in human life. There are many very useful values conveyed through the signs in the show, but the audience commonly capture it as a form of entertainment only through the beauty of the puppeteers' swaying in bringing the puppets to life, the music as well as the female and male voices accompany the show.

Lombok has one famous puppet show, namely *Wong Menak Jayangrane* story. Wong Menak Jayangrane is the most famous wayang story in Lombok. Therefore, this attracts the researchers to investigae further the meanings or lessons contained in *serat menak* puppet show, especially Jayengrana character, through a semiotic point of view.

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RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, researchers chose semiotics as a tool to see every sign that can be interpreted into meaning so that researchers find out implied meanings in characterization of *Wong Menak* symbolically.

1. Theoretical Framework

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Data collection will be done by observation, interviews, and document collection. The stages of data analysis use interactive analysis model consist of four steps in carrying out the analysis process, namely data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing." (Sugiyono, 2015; 345)

Symbolic Values in Wayang Perform

In puppet shows, all thing seen in the show is a value that is displayed symbolically. These values captured indirectly through the characters of each actor. However, based on the data that researchers obtained, almost all of the symbolic values contained in the show are depicted in Jayengrana character.

It doesn't mean to discriminate other characters. Every actor has their own character. However, as the main actor, jayengrane knows how to respond each character of his friends.

In addition, symbolic values contained Wong Menak character are depicted for each name given for every episode. Every name has its own interpretation and meaning.

1. Symbolic Meaning of Jayengrana actor/

As mentioned above, the analysis of meaning on Jayengrana's character in this study conducted through a signification process accordance Roland Barthes' significance theory. This signification process followed two stages of meaning: first stage called denotation, and the second stage called connotation. The straightforward meaning will be conveyed in the denotation meaning, and the meaning generated on the basis of signs and signifiers from the first meaning will be conveyed in the connotation meaning.

a. Identity Symbol

Denotative Meaning: Self-identity

Connotative meaning : Jayengrana character in wong menak puppet has many names. Every name reflects their own character or identity. Identity is a oneself reflection or other people's perception of us. In this case, the identity in *Serat Menak* refers to Jayengrane's self-identity in the *Wong Menak* Wayang Sasak story. Then the true identity intended to Sayyidina Hamzah's struggle or known as Amir Hamzah/Amir Ambyah in spreading the teachings of Islam. Thus, each name has given for each episode of *Wong Menak puppet* becomes a symbol of identity that is interpreted to the original own name.

b. Heroism symbol

Denotative meaning : A person known for their bravery and sacrifice for the truth.

Connotative meaning : Bravery is usually associated with courage, as well as heroism. In this case the two traits become one whole and show a symbol of heroism. This heroism symbol implies courage and sacrifice, as well as describing the might, determination, strength, and magic possessed by Wong Agung in his efforts to conquer his enemies. However, heroes not only a person who failed in war against their enemy as Indonesian people interpret it generally, but heroes is a person who does small

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thing but it meaningful/usefull. One of the true examples is parents. In wong menak story, Amir Hamzah not only able to taking many countries enemy, but also is able to change and inspire the enemy into better people. This can also be categorized as a hero. So, it is appropriate if these traits become a symbol of his heroism

c. Simplicity Symbol

Denotative meaning: unpretentious

Connotation meaning: As a wanderer, Jayengrana has much better adaptability than person isn't wanderer. A wanderer never discriminates person to the others. Therefore, wanderer are able to live anywhere, and under any circumstances. This illustrates, presents dealing with simple and humble on him. In this case, these two things become symbol for Wong Agung. This is seen from his fashion or wearing a dress styl. Jayengrana has very good position and known as famous leader but his character humble and simple.

d. Leadership Symbol

Denotative Meaning: Leader

Connotative Meaning: Jayengrana famous for being wise, just and prudent character. Those three characters have own characteristics of each. when all character put together will become a very extraordinary unity. A person who has these three character refers to a leader. Because, the leader need those three character to lead and making government system runs well. Therefore, these three character are symbols for leadership that find out in Amirul mukminin

e. Strength And Loyalty Symbol

Denotative Meaning: strong and tough and brave

Connotative Meaning: a famous leader is ordinary thing or phenomenon. Even a leader known has many wives also an ordinary phenomenon. But all those thing have closely related. Sayyidina hamzah is famous for all his good qualities, courage, agility, magic, and everything good in him. This thing becomes the cause of the second signs which is having many wives. Because of his fame he was known in various countries and made many women fall in love with him. Therefore he is also signed as a symbol of might. Because he is not only strong on the battlefield, but also in the aisle. This shows his courage and romanticism for humans. He is not only succeeded for conquering many countries, but also he is able to conquering love and marrying the princes who comes from the country had taken. This is relate with the Javanese warrior motto of "mbedah praja mboyong putri" (conquering the enemy's country and taking his daughter). However, what is most important in this symbol of might is his loyalty. He was mighty in all the ways mentioned, but he kept one consort until the end of his life.

CONCLUSION

Based on the description above, it can be conclude that there are five symbols describes Wong Agung Jayengrana. Those five symbols are; 1) identity symbol describes the self identity and reflects the owner name and title pinned. 2) heroism symbols describing his agility and skill in fighting and conquering enemies, 3) simplicity symbol describes his unpretentious self through his wanderings, 4) leadership symbol describes his justice, wisdom, and wisdom in leading, and 5) a symbol of might and loyalty describing his might not only on the battlefield but also in the aisle. He had many wives, but only kept one queen until the end of his life.

From these symbols, it can be concluded that the symbolic meanings of the Jayengrana character Wong Menak Sasak story are contained in naming and characterization in playing his role as the main character. Each name that is pinned on him reflects his identity or identity which is reflected in the character he shows in each of his performance.

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